

TYPES OF SIMILARITIES AND THEIR ESSENCE

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Annotation

This article analyzes the types of similes and reveals their essence. The article classifies similes into metaphors and direct similes based on their figurative nature. It also analyzes the lexical units that form similes, the positive and negative aspects of similes, free similes, playful similes, colloquial similes, and artistic similes with examples.

Keywords: direct similes, positive and negative similes, metaphors, colloquial similes, and artistic similes.

Introduction

A metaphor is a means of describing something or an event similar to another. Typically, conjunctions like "like," "as," and "such as" are used in similes. For example, through expressions like "heart like a fire" or "eyes shone like flames," one thing is compared to another and similarities are emphasized. Similes are not only a linguistic device but also a reflection of culture and mentality.

The main essence of similes consists of the following:

Comparison: A simile demonstrates similarities between multiple phenomena, objects, or concepts.

Imagery: Through similes, it is possible to bring an event or description to life. This is particularly important in literature for conveying imagery in stories or epics.

Expansion of meanings: With the help of similes, the meaning of the depicted object is expanded and deepened, including metaphors and other figurative devices.

2. Types of Similes:

Similes are divided into several types based on their nature and structure:

Direct simile: This type involves a clear and straightforward comparison of similarities between objects or phenomena.

For example: "His heart is as wide as a river" or "Her eyes shone like stars."

Introductory similes: In this type, additional explanations or details are provided before the similes, which further expands the meaning of the imagery.

For example: "A person who spreads his roots on the ground like a tree."

Positive and negative similes: similes can be positive or negative. Positive comparisons compare an event to something good or acceptable, while negative comparisons compare events that lead to nothing good.

Positive: "His heart is as strong as stone."

Negative: "His words are like a light breeze."

Metaphor: Another form of simile is metaphor. A metaphor is a condensed form of comparison, where the comparison itself disappears and one thing is depicted as another. For example, phrases like "Life is a journey" or "Wasting time" are metaphors. This form is frequently encountered in Uzbek folk epics.

Playful comparison: Regarding the unique role of comparisons in expressing the thinking of Turkic peoples, we will focus on this excerpt from the Alpomish epic.

"The spirited horses clattered along, (Bedov otlari dirkillab)
Fluttering like swift birds in flight. (Olg'ir qushdayin charqillab)"

A metaphor can be considered a shortened form of a simile.

The lexical tools that form similes include particles such as *kabi* (like), *singari* (as), *go 'yo* (as if), *xuddi* (just like), *misli*, *misoli*, *bamisli*, and others.

Grammatical means that create similes include suffixes like *-day* (-like), *-dek*, *-simon* (-shaped), *ona-larcha* (like), and many more.

The main feature that enhances the figurative expressiveness in similes is

extraordinary comparison. If the shared characteristic between the compared objects or events is already known in advance, such similes are less likely to enhance the expressiveness of speech. Accordingly, similes can be divided into **two types:**

1. General speech similes
2. Literary similes

The object and subject of general speech comparisons are known in advance. Based on artistic comparisons, a characteristic unknown to many is compared. Viewing simile only as an artistic device leads to a narrowing of its function in the speech process. Comparison is an ornament of speech, a linguistic phenomenon, which serves expressiveness and expressiveness even outside of artistic speech. *Free similes* are the author's own original similes, which determine the writer's skill. For example,

Beneath you, your steed pants like a bird in flight,
 (Ostingda bedoving halloslar qushday)
 Your anger burns like a bitter, frozen winter night.
 (Achchig'ing chillali muzlagan qishday)

"The excerpt presents a beautiful and realistic depiction of a complex emotional state, the main and wonderful content of which finds its subtle expression in the first two lines, and the next two lines further clarify this expression. At the same time, it's extremely original and perfectly suited for the current situation.

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